

Comparing cooling strategies to assess thermal comfort resilience of residential buildings in Barcelona for present and future heatwaves

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ABSTRACT

Future summers are expected to see an increase in the intensity and duration of heat waves due to the effects of climate change. As a consequence, the thermal resilience of actual buildings might not be sufficient to keep comfortable conditions for their inhabitants. Cooling strategies to keep the houses fresh and cool will assume more and more importance as the severity of these climatic events will intensify. Several simulations have been performed to compare how a selected case study apartment behaves with passive measures like natural ventilation and active measures, like mechanical ventilation and air conditioning. Two different types of behaviours are discerned, depending on the commitment of the user and its willingness to take measures to counteract the building overheating. The effect of retrofitting is taken into account as well. The simulations make use of historic data from the summer of 2018 and 2022 and future climate scenarios of the summer of 2030 and 2050. Results highlight how external overheating progressively degrades the thermal resilience of the building with ventilation scenarios, but how air conditioning is more appropriate to keep comfortable conditions inside the house. The behaviour is fundamental, as an aware user can significantly increase comfort in the case of natural ventilation and reduce energy consumption averagely by 15% in case of the air conditioning.

KEYWORDS

Climate adaptation, heatwave, thermal comfort resilience, residential buildings, cooling,

1 INTRODUCTION

Summers of recent years have seen an increase in the intensity and severity of heat waves and events related to extreme heat. On the 11th of August 2021, the meteorological station of SIAS (Servizio Informativo Agrometeorologico Siciliano) in Syracuse, Italy, recorded 48.8° C, the highest maximum temperature ever monitored in the whole European continent (1), beating the previous record of 48.0° C of the 10th of July 1977 in Athens (2). In Spain, on the 15th of August

2021, 47.0° C was recorded in Alcantarilla, Murcia, reaching a new record for the stations by AEMET (Agencia Estatal de Meteorología). This fact was not an isolated phenomenon, as a quarter of all the meteorological stations (twenty-four stations) recorded the highest temperature for August that year, while a fifth of them (nineteen stations) registered their highest value ever during the same month (3). During July 2022, twenty-nine stations recorded the highest temperature ever again, beating the records of the past year. Forty-one stations recorded the highest maximum monthly average temperature (4). The situation was not better in Catalonia, where the months of June, July and August 2022 have been the warmest in 20 years for half of the meteorological stations, while for the rest, the second most warm (5). The effect of such summers is amplified in cities, as they usually present a higher ambient temperature than proximal rural areas. The urban heat island phenomenon has been noticed in more than 400 cities in the world (6).

Barcelona, among other cities in the world, has developed a Climatic Plan (7) to respond to and counteract this emergency, which affects several aspects of life in the city. Concrete objectives for 2030 include, among others the retrofit of 20% of buildings older than 40 years, creating 1.6 km more of green areas, reach zero energy poverty (7). Heat has a direct effect on health, and diminishes the quality of life of residents and their safety. A review of studies on the effects caused by elevated indoor temperatures found out the most common concern is about respiratory health, diabetes management, core schizophrenia and dementia symptoms (8). In general, an inadequate indoor temperature is associated with poor health status (9). Other studies assess the potential economic impact on the healthcare system when retrofitting vulnerable housing, and improving indoor conditions and the health of occupants (10). A study from Gasparrini et al. (11) relates the mortality rates in various cities across the world with the ambient temperature of the site. Different populations do not have the same values of mortality for the same temperatures, because of acclimatization, adaptation and difference in variability factors. Nevertheless, mortality is at its minimum at a certain temperature and increases moving to colder and warmer temperatures for a common pattern. In particular, mortality usually rises slowly and linearly for cold temperatures and escalates quickly and non-linearly for warmer temperatures (11). Again, a nonlinear correlation has been noticed between relative risk (RR) of cause-specific mortality and duration and excess of hot nights (12). Another study by Alberdi et al. (13), looking for a correlation between atmospheric variables and deaths, found that during the warm season there is a positive correlation between maximum temperature and deaths by organic causes. Indeed, this variable was found to be a significant predictor of mortality. Based on these results, the Spanish Ministry of Health developed an index on the risk to people's health caused by excess temperature, called MOMO (14). Alberdi et al. (13) also investigated the role of relative humidity and found out that in Madrid's mesothermal Mediterranean climate, mortality was negatively affected. This means a decrease in relative humidity was linked to an increase in mortality. When talking about thermal comfort instead, the role of relative humidity is more complex, as it depends also on the climate adaptation of people. A study by Kong et al. (15) revealed that at 25 and 28°C people have more or less the same perception of humidity when it is below 70%. Above this value, people start showing stronger thermal responses. If at 25 °C the sensation was similar for all the interviewed, at 28° C a difference can be noticed between people coming from a region with a low humidity climate (having a stronger sensation) and people from a climate with a hi humidity (weaker

feeling). Thermal sensation and comfort also strongly depend on personal factors like the age of people. It has been found that elderly people have lower sensitivity for temperatures, leading to a wider comfort range than younger adults. The difference between the level at which people feel thermally neutral between the two groups can reach up to 2.4° C (16).

The thermal comfort of people has a lot to do with the buildings they live in and their thermal resilience. The word “resilience” comes from the Latin word “resilio”, meaning “to bounce back” (17). This concept can be applied to various fields of study, like cities and buildings. Urban resilience is defined as “The capacity of individuals, communities, institutions, businesses, and systems within a city to survive, adapt, and grow no matter what kinds of chronic stresses and acute shocks they experience” (18). Therefore, thermal resilience of the built environment can be defined as the ability of a building to withstand external stresses while maintaining comfortable conditions indoors. The idea is closely related to the concept of passive architecture, which according to Rahmah et al. (19), is the ability of a building to shield occupants from external climatic events, so that comfort conditions are naturally achieved inside. When talking about the summer period and the risk of overheating, the building design is not the only important factor, as also some cooling strategies can highly influence thermal behaviour. These strategies can be active or passive, depending on the fact they use energy or not. Kuczyński et al. (20) concluded that for a temperate climate (UK), putting into practice passive strategies like night ventilation, solar shading and having a high thermal mass can successfully prevent overheating. Another study for Germany by Schünemann et al. (21) found that an optimal behaviour operating cross ventilation can reduce summer indoor temperatures by 2-3°C. In a mild climate as in California, natural ventilation can guarantee thermal comfort to occupants of commercial buildings with the potential of savings on energy consumption with respect to air conditioning (22). An earlier study by Agrawal (23) found that, at the global level, passive strategies can reduce by 2.35% energy consumption in the building. A study by Ortiz et al. (24) shows how a building with natural ventilation generally suffers less than one-third of overheating hours than a building without. The correct use of awnings has an important influence as well. Nevertheless, it is possible that, in the event of heat waves, passive measures might not always be enough to grant comfort (22). Active measures allow having better indoor comfort even during periods of high temperatures. The most common ones are usually mechanical ventilation and air conditioning. Fans are considered an intermediate strategy with many beneficial effects on thermal comfort. The air movement they cause ameliorates the thermal exchange for convection around the human body, making them a good strategy for warm climates (25). Indeed, simple desk fans can elevate up to 3 K the temperature at which users feel a neutral thermal sensation (26). This is an important factor which allows the extension of acceptable set point temperature and larger usage of natural ventilation, thus reducing energy demand for cooling. The study on Brazilian buildings by André et al. (27) reveals the use of mechanical air movement only could generate 20-40% energy saving on cooling without compromising thermal comfort for the occupants.

The present study wants to contribute to the research in thermal building resilience during intense heat periods by simulating different cooling strategies, including passive and active measures. The selected case study makes use of a reference building from the typical building stock of Barcelona. The choice has been made as this archetype and its thermal characteristics have already been

largely investigated in (10,24,28). The simulations are performed with historical meteorological data from recent summers and with future climate projections, under the consequences of climate change. The aim is to analyse how the buildings will change their behaviour in the foreseen scenarios of increased extreme heat events during summer.

The structure of this paper is as follows: Chapter 2 first (2.1) explains the model defined as a case study, the selected data for occupation profile and meteorological data (2.2) describes the cooling strategies and (2.3) enlists the discomfort and risk indicators adopted to assess the thermal resilience. Chapters 3 and 4 are dedicated to results and conclusions.

2 METHODOLOGY

A total of forty detailed dynamic simulations of a reference apartment have been performed. They consider the occupancy behaviour and compare four different climatic scenarios, five cooling strategies and two envelopes types with the software TRNSYS 18 (29).

2.1 Case study

2.1.1 Building data

The apartment selected is located in a multifamily building built between 1951 and 1980, belonging to typology F indicated by (30). A reference building of this typology represents half of the residential stock in Barcelona. Three people live in the flat, each one sleeping in a different bedroom. Additionally, the apartment is provided with a kitchen, a living room and two bathrooms. Usually, this kind of building has six floors (five plus the ground floor). For this study, the apartment is located on an intermediate floor. **Error! Reference source not found.** contains the main characteristics of the envelope.

Component	U [W/m ²]	Thickness [m]
External wall	1.223	0.23
External roof	1.170	0.34
External partition	2.254	0.18
Internal partition	2.465	0.09
Internal floor	1.863	0.28
Component	U [W/m ²]	g [%]
Window (1.1x0.8)	5.68	85

Table 1 - Building envelope thermal characteristics retrieved from the Catalan building typology F (30)

2.1.2 Stochastic occupancy model

As the cooling strategies implemented are often depending on the presence and activity of the occupants, the simulation uses a stochastic model with probability profiles of occupancy and energy-consuming activities from the work of Tejero et al. (28). The model provides as well information to calculate the internal gains: the fraction for the occupancy is distributed among the zones of the apartment depending on the time of the day (day and night use). For the lighting fraction of gains, the model has a daylight control system integrated with the data of occupation and activity from the stochastic model.

2.1.3 Meteorological data

Data used for the simulations are retrieved from two databases. Historical data from 2018 and 2022 are provided by the meteorological station of “Badalona Museu” (31), located close to the centre of Badalona, a coastal town which constitutes, together with Sant’Adrià de Besós and Santa Coloma de Gramenet, a unique conurbation expanding on the northern border of Barcelona municipality. A preliminary analysis of data from these two years shows how, even if the highest maximum temperature is reached in august 2018, 2022 has been averagely warmer, as all the minimum and maximum average temperatures are higher than in the previous year. Numbers can be found in Table 2.

	2018			2022		
	Jun	Jul	Aug	Jun	Jul	Aug
Average Temperature	21.8	25.2	25.8	23.8	26.0	26.7
Maximum absolute Temperature	27.7	30.4	35.8	30.8	30.9	33.2
Average of daily Maximum Temperatures	23.4	27.2	28.1	26.4	28.1	29.3
Minimum absolute Temperature	15.7	18.8	18.8	18.6	20.3	18.7
Average of daily Minimum Temperatures	19.5	22.5	23.2	21.6	23.8	23.4

Table 2 – Temperature data from historical meteorological records of 2018 and 2022 in comparison.

To evaluate the effect of climate change, two future weather input files were elaborated using the software Meteonorm (32). These additional data are representative of two extremely hot summers in 2030 and 2050 in the same location, under the most probable baseline scenario (RCP4.5) proposed by the IPCC (33).

The simulated period goes from the 10th of May to the 31st of August for 2022 and from the 10th of May to the 30th of September for 2018, 2030 and 2050 of each one of the selected years, but the study will analyse the summer months of June, July, August and September. A representative heatwave has been selected for each year of simulation.

2.1.4 Definition of heatwave

The term “heatwave” is generally referred to a period of unusual heat (of at least three consecutive days), during which the temperature exceeds some established thresholds, but there is not still a worldwide recognized definition. This happens because there are different types of climate, and the same temperature might mean different things from one place to another.

According to the municipality of Barcelona, a heatwave occurs when the maximum temperature surpasses, for at least three consecutive days, 33.1° C. This definition has been crafted by looking at climatic data from the period between 1971 and 2000 (34).

Langlois et al. (35) proposed another methodology for defining a heatwave period, based on the Excess Heat Factor (EHF), calculated on two indexes, defined in Eq. 1 and Eq. 2:

$$EHI_{sig} = \frac{(T_i + T_{i+1} + T_{i+2})}{3} - T_{95} \quad (1)$$

$$EHI_{accl} = \frac{(T_i + T_{i+1} + T_{i+2})}{3} - \frac{(T_{i-1} + \dots + T_{i-30})}{30} \quad (2)$$

The Significance Excess Heat Index (EHI_{sig}) is the difference between the average temperature of a three-day period and the 95th percentile of the daily average temperature of the reference climate.

The Acclimatisation Excess Heat Index (EHI_{accl}) measures if a period of three days is hotter than the previous 30 days.

The EHF is the product of the EHI_{sig} with the maximum between EHI_{accl} and 1 (Eq. 3).

$$EHF = EHI_{sig} \cdot \max(1, EHI_{accl}) \quad (3)$$

It has to be intended as an expression of the long-term temperature anomaly, amplified by the short-term temperature anomaly (36). Any positive value of this factor indicates the heatwave conditions are met.

Information on the increasing severity of the extreme heat events and the effect rising temperatures might have in selected future years compared to actual summers is provided in Table 3. Tropical nights are defined as nights when the temperature does not go below 20° C, while torrid nights are above 25° C (7) (tropical nights also include torrid nights). The last row instead indicates the number of days in which the thermometer reaches 33.1° C, i.e. the indication of a heatwave according to the Municipality of Barcelona (34).

Indicator	2018	2022	2030	2050
Tropical nights	92	98	97	103
Torrid Nights	7	15	27	42
Days with more than 33.1 °C	2	1	20	34
Days with positive EHF	9	27	29	66

Table 3 - Summary of tropical nights, torrid nights, days in which the temperature rises above 33.1° C, and with positive EHF in the considered climatic scenarios.

In 2018, the temperature in Badalona surpassed 33.1 for only two consecutive days. Even if summer 2022 was very warm, as explained in section 1, a heatwave was not detected (in Badalona) according to the definition of the municipality of Barcelona (34), i.e. the temperature did not rise above 33.1°C for three consecutive days. In 2030 and 2050 instead, heatwaves according to this definition are identifiable.

Applying the definition of Excess Heat Factor to the meteorological data (historical of 2018 and 2022 and future of 2030 and 2050), and using a 95th percentile calculated using the average daily temperatures of 10 years (from 2011 to 2021) of data from the station “Badalona Museu”, an increasing number of periods with heatwave conditions are identified going further in the future. The quantity and duration of these periods might be overestimated in future scenarios, as the 95th percentile of temperature is expected to vary and increase with the general trend of rising temperatures.

For purposes of the analysis, it has been necessary to select two weeks of intense heat for each year.

Year	Heatwave selected period	Heatwave definition met
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2018	27 Jul – 10 Aug	EHF
2022	1 Aug – 14 Aug	EHF
2030	29 Jul – 11 Aug	EHF, Barcelona Municipality
2050	18 Jul – 1 Aug	EHF, Barcelona Municipality

Table 4 resumes the chosen periods and indicate which of the explained definition of heatwave they respect.

Year	Heatwave selected period	Heatwave definition met
2018	27 Jul – 10 Aug	EHF
2022	1 Aug – 14 Aug	EHF
2030	29 Jul – 11 Aug	EHF, Barcelona Municipality
2050	18 Jul – 1 Aug	EHF, Barcelona Municipality

Table 4 – Selected heatwave period for the simulation and definition met between EHF (35) and Municipality of Barcelona (34).

Error! Reference source not found. shows the used meteorological data and the future projections for the simulated period from June to September. The upper graph plots the temperatures and highlights the selected heatwave period for the purposes of this study. On the lower graph, the EHF is plotted for the same period, with emphasis on positive EHF. All the selected periods (apart from 2022) find the two definitions in accordance.

Figure 1 – Meteorological data (2018, 2022) and future projections (2030, 2050) for the period June-September. The upper graphs show the ambient temperature of the site and the lower ones plot the EHF calculated with the meteorological data. Periods

highlighted in orange correspond to the selected heatwave for the simulation. Periods highlighted in red correspond to periods with more than 33.1° C of maximum (upper graph) and periods when the EHF is positive (lower graph).

2.2 Cooling strategies

Five different strategies are explored to cool down the apartment during the summer months, depending on the equipment in possession of the user and his behaviour, which can be fixed or aware. The difference depends on the commitment to act for improving the thermal comfort of the house (e.g. opening or closing windows, awnings, etc.).

The first two scenarios simulate a combination of vernacular strategies known since the past in the Mediterranean region: natural ventilation and solar shading. They are considered passive, as they do not need any external source of energy (e.g. electricity). Natural ventilation consists in opening the windows on different sides of the house when certain conditions are met, so a pressure difference can cause the external air to enter the rooms and remove the excess heat accumulated inside. This is especially efficient at night, when the temperature usually drops and helps the house to discharge the thermal energy absorbed during the day. Solar shading instead consists in blocking the entrance of direct solar radiation into the house. As in summer, especially in the Mediterranean climate, these bring a lot of energy inside, and they have a huge contribution to overheating. Shading is more effective if done with external awnings.

The air change hours due to natural ventilation are obtained under the hypothesis of cross-side ventilation, as suggested by the British Standard 5925:1991(37). Solar shading instead, depends on control of the radiation on each façade of the building.

The first two scenarios of Natural Ventilation, are:

- *Natural Ventilation – Fixed (NATVENT-F)*: Natural ventilation is implemented based on occupancy and temperature, only as night ventilation between 0 am and 7 am. Blinds are closed when both temperature and total radiation on the external surface exceed the thresholds of 24.5°C and 140 W/m² respectively, while blinds are opened if the temperature falls below 24.5°C or radiation falls below 120 W/m². In the fixed scenario, this happens only when the household is occupied (blinds are open during unoccupied hours); the maximum opaque fraction of blinds is 50%.
- *Natural Ventilation – Aware (NATVENT-A)*: Natural ventilation; is implemented with the same occupancy and temperature control if the dwelling is occupied by at least one person. Natural ventilation is activated when the average indoor operative temperature ranges between 24.5°C and 28°C or when the indoor temperature exceeds both 28°C and the ambient temperature. Solar shading is implemented based only on temperature and solar radiation, as explained in the previous scenario, but independently from the occupancy. The opaque fraction of the blind is increased to 70%.

The third type of ventilation makes use of electric fans to increase the air velocity in the rooms of the apartment. This strategy does not directly affect the temperature of the room but influences the thermal perception of the people. According to McIntyre (38), and Rohles et al (39), people under ceiling fans producing an air velocity of more than 1 m/s feel comfortable with temperatures as high as 30 °C. Air movement, climatically adapted clothing and the possibility to have control over

the environment (opening windows, switching on or off fans) have an impact on thermal perception (22).

The conditions that push people into turning on fans in their houses depend on several factors, including personal perception and the specific climate and habits of the place they live. According to Nicol (40), 60% of occupants are expected to switch fans on when the indoor operative temperature goes beyond 25°C. A review of more studies by He et al. (41) suggests in offices this could more probably be around 28°C.

For mechanical ventilation, only aware behaviour is considered, as fans require active control.

- *Mechanical Ventilation (MECVENT)*: The fans are switched on in a room when the operative temperature goes beyond 28° C and someone is occupying it. The only rooms provided with fans are the kitchen and the bedrooms (with a 40 W desk fan) and the living room (with a 60 W ceiling fan). Natural ventilation and solar shading follow the same strategy as in the case of the Natural Ventilation - Aware scenario.

Another common practice for cooling the house is air conditioning. The survey conducted for the Catalan Housing Agency in the framework of the MARIE project collected data on the habits of people living in this region (42). Around 55% of houses of typology F had air conditioning in 2016, and most of the interviewees were setting the summer thermostat between 23 and 25° C.

The reference household is provided with a heat pump of 6.60 kW of refrigeration power producing water at 7° C. It produces refrigerated water which is stored in a tank of inertia connected to a single fan coil of 5.08 kW (cold) of capacity ($T_{in\ water} = 7^{\circ}C$, $T_{out\ water} = 12^{\circ}C$). The refrigerated air is brought to the living room and the bedrooms by connected air ducts. Since there are again different ways of making use of air conditioning, the current study hypothesized two behavioural patterns.

- *Air Conditioning – Fixed (AC-F)*: the fixed user switches on air conditioning in the served rooms (living room and bedrooms). The thermostat is in the living room and is set to 26°C. Additionally, solar shading as in the Natural Ventilation – fixed scenario.
- *Air Conditioning – Aware (AC-A)*: the aware user sets the thermostat in the living room to 26° C (served rooms are the same), and does natural ventilation in the rooms without air conditioning (i.e.: kitchen and bathrooms, which is possible as they are connected by the corridor). Natural Ventilation and solar shading follow the same algorithm as in the Natural Ventilation – aware scenario.

An overview of all the described scenarios is shown in Table 5 – Summary of the main characteristics of each scenario. Table 5.

	NATVENT-F	NATVENT-A	MECVENT	AC-A	AC-F
NAT VENT	If between 0 AM and 7 AM AND OCC AND [24.5<T _{op} <28 OR (T _{op} >28 AND T _{op} >T _{amb})]	If OCC AND [24.5<T _{op} <28 OR (T _{op} >28 AND T _{op} >T _{amb})]	If OCC AND [24.5<T _{op} <28 OR (T _{op} >28 AND T _{op} >T _{amb})]	If OCC AND [24.5<T _{op} <28 OR (T _{op} >28 AND T _{op} >T _{amb})] <i>Only in the kitchen and in the bathrooms</i>	-

MECH VENT	-	-	If OCC AND Top>28 <i>only in the occupied rooms</i>	-	-
SOL SHAD	If T _{op} >24.5 AND I>140 W/m ² AND If OCC Opaque fraction: 50%	If T _{op} >24.5 AND I>140 W/m ² Opaque fraction: 70%	If T _{op} >24.5 AND I>140 W/m ² Opaque fraction: 70%	If T _{op} >24.5 AND I>140 W/m ² Opaque fraction: 70%	If T _{op} >24.5 AND I>140 W/m ² AND If OCC Opaque fraction: 50%
AC	-	-	-	T _{op,sal} >26 <i>only in the living room and bedrooms</i>	If T _{op,sal} >26 <i>only in the living room and bedrooms</i>

• Table 5 – Summary of the main characteristics of each scenario. OCC means there is someone in the dwelling.

To evaluate the impact of the envelope in these simulations, the simulations are repeated with a thermally improved reference building. The measures adopted include typical retrofit solutions that can be implemented in already existing houses. Ortiz et al. (24) made an extensive analysis to develop cost-optimal studies for the energy refurbishment of residential buildings in Catalonia. The selected combination of measures (described in Table 6) external insulation with expanded polystyrene of 8 cm and new PVC windows (as the reference building has wooden ones) with double glass 4/16/4.

Component	U [W/m ²]	Thickness [m]
External wall	0.348	0.31
Component	U [W/m ²]	g [%]
Window (1.1x0.8)	1.12	66

Table 6 - New thermal characteristics of the retrofitted building.

2.3 Thermal resilience indicators

A list of thermal comfort indicators for measuring thermal resilience starting from the ones used by Avanzini et al. (43), has been adapted for the specific case study. Before explaining each of them, some important definitions for the following formulas are presented.

The running mean outdoor temperature ($T_{o,m}$) is calculated with the definition by EN 16789-1 (44), where $T_{\text{outdoor } d-i}$ is the average daily outdoor temperature for the i -th previous day.

The operative temperatures used in the simulation are calculated by TRNSYS according to the definition of ISO 7730 (45) and ASHRAE (46) with Eq. 4:

$$T_{op} = \frac{h_c T_a + h_r T_{mr}}{h_c + h_r} \quad (4)$$

Where: T_a the air temperature, T_r the mean radiant temperature, h_c the heat exchange coefficient by convection, and h_r the heat exchange coefficient by radiation (29) and are automatically calculated by the simulation software.

2.3.1 Adaptive comfort model

The adaptive comfort model is based on comfort acceptability thresholds according to external temperatures. Indeed, it is valid only for occupants doing sedentary activities without strict

clothing policies, i.e. allowed to vary their clothing factor depending on their sensation and indoor and/or outdoor thermal conditions (47). Additionally, they can open and close elements in the building envelope, such as windows, and ventilation flaps, to modify the thermal conditions (44). The adaptive comfort model identifies four categories of comfort during summer, which depend on the external temperature. CAT I is the range closer to the optimal conditions. The other thresholds are defined in the following equation by substituting ΔT_{CAT} with 2, 3 and 4, for categories II, III and IV respectively. Eq. 5 is valid for $T_{o,rm}$ between 10 and 30° C; outside of this range, the categories are considered constant.

$$T_{i,CAT} = 0.33 \cdot T_{o,rm} \pm 18.8 \cdot \Delta T_{CAT} \quad (5)$$

As this formula is defined for a building without mechanical cooling, EN 16789 (44) provides a corrective factor for an increased air velocity, increasing the distance of the ranges from the T_{rm} . The chosen corrective factor of 1.2 K for an indoor air speed of 0.6 m/s (44), is considered adequate for a user doing mainly a sedentary activity (48). This correction is applied only in the Mechanical Ventilation scenario when fans are running to reflect the positive impact of the fans on comfort.

2.3.2 Heat Index

The Heat Index (HI), combines relative humidity with air temperature and represents the human-perceived equivalent temperature in shaded areas. The formula (Eq. 6) is proposed by Rothfusz (49):

$$HI = 0.5 \cdot [T_{op} + 61 + 1.2 \cdot (T_{op} - 68) + 0.094 \cdot RH] \quad (6)$$

with T_{op} as the operative temperature (in F) and RH as the relative humidity (in %). If HI is higher than 80F, it is necessary to use the regression equation proposed by Rothfusz (49).

The alert system by the United States National Weather Service divides the HI into four risk bands identified in °C: Caution (27<HI<32), possibly leading to fatigue; Extreme Caution (32<HI<41), possibly leading to a heat stroke, cramps or exhaustion; Danger (41<HI<52), likely leading to heat cramps or exhaustion; Extreme danger (HI>52), highly likely leading to heat stroke (50).

To take into account the effect of mechanical ventilation on HI, the operative temperatures have been diminished by a ΔT of 1.2 K in a room with fans and only when they are working. Subsequently, HI is calculated with the adjusted T_{op} .

2.3.3 Humidex

The Humidex (H) expresses how hot the average person feels about the weather. It takes into account the effect of temperature and humidity (dew point). The Humidex is the HI equivalent used by the Canadian warning system (51), which defines five discomfort bands: Noticeable Discomfort (30<H<35); Evident Discomfort (35<H<40); Intense Discomfort (40<H<45); Dangerous Discomfort (45<H<55), or possible heat stroke; Heat Stroke Probable (H>55). The formula (Eq. 7) (52) is:

$$H = T_{air} + 0.555 \cdot (E - 10) \quad (7)$$

with T_{air} as the air temperature of the zone (in °C) and E as the vapour pressure (in hPa), given by Eq 8 (T_{dew} is the dew point in K).

$$E = 6.11 \cdot e^{5417.7530 \cdot \left[\left(\frac{1}{273.16} \right) - \left(\frac{1}{T_{dew}} \right) \right]} \quad (8)$$

2.3.4 Indoor Overheating Degree (IOD), Ambient Warmness Degree (AWD) and Overheating Escalation Factor

The Indoor Overheating Degree (IOD) (53) takes into account different comfort limits for separate dwelling zones and follows the particular occupant's behaviour. In the current study, the formula (Eq. 9) is simplified by considering the average temperature of all zones.

$$IOD = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N [(T_{op,i} - T_{comf})^+ \cdot t_i]}{\sum_{i=1}^N t_i} \quad (9)$$

With $T_{op,i}$ and T_{comf} are the operative temperature and the comfort threshold (in °C) at the time t_i and N is the number of occupied hours. For this paper's sake, this data is calculated for a T_{comf} of 26°C and the upper adaptive comfort thresholds ($T_{i,CAT}$).

To quantify the warmness of a given climate scenario, Hamdy et al. (53) introduced the Ambient Warmness Degree (AWD) (Eq. 10), which considers both the accumulation of amplitude and the duration of each occurrence against a base temperature of 18°C.

$$AWD_{18^\circ\text{C}} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N [(T_{amb,i} - 18^\circ\text{C})^+ \cdot t_i]}{\sum_{i=1}^N t_i} \quad (10)$$

With $T_{amb,i}$ as the ambient air temperature. The Overheating Escalation Factor (α_{IOD}), is calculated as the ratio between IOD and AWD and indicates the sensitivity of households to outdoor overheating (Eq 11).

$$\alpha_{IOD} = IOD / AWD_{18^\circ\text{C}} \quad (11)$$

In other terms, its ability to maintain comfortable indoor conditions despite heat stress. Indeed it represents the difference between external and internal overheating. If α_{IOD} is over 1, it means that the dwelling is not able to withstand the heat. On the contrary, an α_{IOD} close to zero indicates that the building is able to counterbalance external overheating. A thermal resilient building should ideally present low values of α_{IOD} no matter the intensity of outdoor warmness.

2.4 Energy Consumption

Energy consumption is extracted from the TRNSYS model together with the other simulation outputs. In particular, the model indicates which is the power of the considered equipment every three minutes. To obtain the energy consumed, this power is multiplied by the amplitude of each time step (three minutes) and then summed for the all period of simulation.

Equipment used in the scenario of Mechanical Ventilation is, as mentioned in section 2.2, three desk fans of 40 W and a ceiling fan of 60 W of power. The starting-up phase of these fans is negligible and their power goes immediately to the nominal value.

Equipment considered in the air conditioning scenarios are the heat pump and the fan coil described in section 2.2.2, and water pumps circulating the heat carrier.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section explains the results from the simulations for each one of the indicators selected and explained in section 2. Each graphic is referred to the meteorological data of a selected year (the whole summer plus a specific focus on the heatwave period) and displays all the scenarios with the old and retrofitted envelope.

3.1 Adaptive Model

Figure 2 shows how much time the dwelling and its retrofit version spend in each category of the adaptive comfort model. For new buildings, CAT I and CAT II are both accepted as comfortable conditions.

In 2018, it looks quite clear how generally, moving from natural ventilation to mechanical and later to the use of air conditioning, the situation improves significantly. Indeed for scenarios of natural ventilation, a part of the time is not in CAT I or CAT II. On the contrary, the air conditioning scenarios are able to keep comfortable conditions always. The adoption of an aware behaviour has a huge impact on natural ventilation and is able to keep the house even in CAT I for most of the time during summer. Fixed behaviour instead always leads to a more uncomfortable situation inside the dwelling. Modifying the envelope characteristics always has a positive effect on the building, as it shifts all the bands towards better conditions.

Compared to 2018, other years follow a similar pattern, although comfort is met more rarely (especially in 2030 and 2050). Ventilation strategies (even in the case of an aware user) will be inefficient to keep the dwelling comfortable. In a probable heatwave of 2050, the house will likely spend little time in comfortable conditions with only natural ventilation (only 13% and 35% if there is also retrofit). Mechanical ventilation can contrast a bit better with the extreme heat, but can not avoid the house to end up in CAT IV for a portion of time in future summers. On the contrary, the comfort of air conditioning scenarios is not affected by the intensity of future extreme heat events (their energy consumption is highly affected though, as explained later on).

As supposed, the heatwave period is more challenging for the dwelling than the whole summer period. A difference can be noted between recent summers: the 2018 heatwave looks more critical than the 2022 one, but if looking at the whole summer, the situation of 2022 is worse than in 2018. In the heatwave of 2022, the retrofit combined with the scenarios of Natural Ventilation -aware allows it to be in CAT I for 92% of the time (compared with 57 % of the same scenario without retrofit). This means the retrofit is not only beneficial for the cold season but can also increase thermal resilience in summer. Probable heatwaves of 2030 and 2050 will see the decline of effectiveness of natural ventilation, although mechanical ventilation will still grant comfort for around half of the time.

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Figure 2 - Share of time spent in each category of the adaptive comfort model for summer 2022, 2030 and 2050. Graphs on the left refer to the heatwave period for each summer, while graphs on the right refer to the period June-September. All scenarios are shown, followed by their retrofit, highlighted by the "R".

3.2 Heat Index

General considerations done in the previous paragraph for the adaptive comfort model apply to Heat Index as well. Nevertheless, this index does not take into account in any way the exterior temperature increase and the adaptation of the people (differently from the adaptive comfort model). Therefore, future scenarios are generally worsening as it is going to be more probable to deal with higher temperatures at home. The results are shown in Figure 3.

During the summer of 2018, NATVENT-A and MECVENT scored similar to air conditioning scenarios, except of AC-F which has a more extended Caution band, 91% compared to 43% in NATVENT-A (but also an Extreme Caution band close to zero). Therefore, the major difference is played by the user's behaviour. AC-F benefits from a much lower comfort than its aware version. MECVENT does not impact the band in which the dwelling places itself when compared to NATVENT-A. Retrofit has a relevant positive effect also on the HI caution bands. That is especially appreciable in the case of natural ventilation.

Similar considerations apply to future years, with a certain variability in the magnitude of the efficacy of retrofit and aware behaviour. Air conditioning almost eliminates the Extreme Caution band and brings back the dwelling to Normal conditions for a fraction of time (except for summer 2050). Results of the simulations show that keeping the dwelling in normal conditions in 2030 and 2050 during a heatwave is not possible. Only in the scenarios of air conditioning, the better situation that can be achieved is being in the Caution band.

Ventilation strategies lose significantly their efficacy in the summer of 2030 and 2050 to keep the house in comfortable HI bands. The difference between the summer and heatwave periods of 2030 and 2050 is little in air conditioning scenarios if compared to ventilation scenarios. That might be because the proposed strategies are not very effective, and interior conditions are still very influenced by the exterior environment, making HI elevate.

Figure 3 - Share of time spent in each Heat Index caution band during summer 2022, 2030 and 2050. Graphs on the left refer to the heatwave period for each summer, while graphs on the right refer to the period June-September. All scenarios are shown, followed by their retrofit, highlighted by the “R”.

Scenarios with air conditioning spend more time in the band Caution than ventilation, but less time in higher bands. Nevertheless, time spent in Normal conditions is not that different from ventilation in future summers. This might be due to the fact the showcased values are averages of the whole apartment conditions, and, according to the hypothesis of the simulations, not all rooms are equipped with an air conditioning input. Indeed, rooms with air conditioning are in the range of Normal (HI) and Little to no discomfort (H) most of the time, as can be noted in Figure 4.

During strong heatwaves, the temperature and humidity might vary from a conditioned room to a non-conditioned one (e.g.: moving from a bedroom to the kitchen). This might be the cause of additional discomfort for the inhabitants.

Figure 4 - Difference between a non-conditioned and a conditioned room on HI (first row). Data are plotted for the scenario of AC – F and 2030 HW as an example, but a similar pattern is visible also during the whole summer period and in the other years.

3.3 Humidex

In general, the results of the other selected index follow a pattern similar to HI. Results are shown in Figure 5.

All years follow a similar pattern. The user's behaviour has again a noticeable effect: an aware behaviour always ameliorates the situation in the case of both ventilation and air conditioning scenarios, shifting up the bands, especially in the past summers of 2018 and 2022. With a hotter summer, such as in 2030 and 2050, the effect is not that impactful anymore - the difference between air conditioning aware and fixed is less than in recent summers if the envelope is the same.

The retrofitting of the building always ameliorates the situation, although not as much as the shift from fixed to aware behaviour.

Simulations reveal with the selected IPCC probable climate scenario, it will not be possible to have a house in the little to no discomfort band during heatwaves. Considerations similar to the ones made in Figure 4 for HI can be applied here as well.

Figure 5 - Share of time spent in each Humidex comfort band during summer 2022, 2030 and 2050. Graphs on the left refer to the heatwave period for each summer, while graphs on the right refer to the period June-September. All scenarios are shown, followed by their retrofit, highlighted by the "R".

3.4 Overheating

Figure 6 and **Error! Reference source not found.** express how the AWD is related to the α_{IOD} calculated with the constant comfort temperature of 26° C (set point of air conditioning) and with the categories of adaptive comfort. Values are calculated over a period of 4 days, according to the methodology adopted for the MOMO index, as this is the period over which high temperatures affect death number (13). The figures aim to analyze visually which is the effectiveness of the strategies to mitigate the overheating of the dwelling in adverse climatic conditions. Having low values of α_{IOD} at high levels of AWD means the building can resist external stress. On the contrary, if at high AWD values, the α_{IOD} increases much, it means the building is not resilient to the external climatic conditions and overheating is escalating. The series are plotted twice (old envelope and retrofitted envelope) to emphasize the effect of the building characteristics. In all cases, the retrofitting is able to shift the curve to lower α_{IOD} values and to decrease the slope of the curve. Figure 6 shows the situation of Natural Ventilation – aware (left) and Mechanical Ventilation (right). At a first sight, adaptive categories are performing better than the fixed comfort temperature, meaning that considering the adaptive comfort model, the building is not overheating as much as if a fixed comfort model is applied. Nevertheless, a linear correlation is found, meaning the mitigation capacity of the dwelling is degrading as the external ambient conditions become more severe. In the case of Mechanical Ventilation and retrofit, if adaptive categories are considered, the overheating is much less evident. In particular, there is a cloud of points highlighted with a circle in the graph on the right, which represents situations in which, although AWD is increasing, the comfort level stays constant. In the case of Natural Ventilation – fixed, the situation was much worse, as already mentioned by Avanzini et al., α_{IOD} for the fixed temperature, reach values close to the unity in 2030 and 2050, meaning the overheating of the house is almost the same as outside.

Figure 6 – Correlation between the Average Warmness Degree (AWD) and Overheating Escalation Factor (α_{IOD}), calculated using adaptive comfort thresholds (IOD_CAT) and fixed comfort temperatures (IOD_26) with Natural Ventilation – aware (left) and Mechanical Ventilation (right) scenarios. Dots are values calculated for four days around every summer day of 2018, 2022, 2030 and 2050 (June-September).

Error! Reference source not found. instead shows a comparison between NATVENT-A, MECVENT and AC-A scenarios. Adaptive categories are not plotted, as for AC-A, they all score zero independently of the outdoor conditions. A building with air conditioning and an aware user

is fully able to neutralize overheating, according to the adaptive comfort model. Nevertheless, if the α_{IOD} concerning a fixed comfort temperature is adopted, a correlation is still found, although the steepness of the curves is much weaker compared to ventilation scenarios.

Error! Reference source not found. highlights the correlation found between HI and external temperature. The information given is similar to Figure 6 and **Error! Reference source not found.**, but with another comfort index. The represented values plotted for NATVENT-A in both building envelopes emphasize the role of the retrofitting measure. The linear regression indicates at which external temperature the simulated envelope enters a dangerous situation for the health of the inhabitants. The effect of the retrofit is visible here as well, stronger the external temperature, and HI reaches higher values.

Figure 7 - Correlation between the Average Warmness Degree (AWD) and Overheating Escalation Factor (α_{IOD}), calculated using fixed comfort temperatures (IOD_26) with NATVENT-A, MECVENT and AC-A scenarios. Dashed lines are retrofits.

Figure 8 - Correlation between external temperature and Heat Index. Dots are average values of four days periods for every summer day of years 2018, 2022, 2030, and 2050 (June- September).

3.5 Overheating vs Energy Use

Figure 9 – Comparison of the energy consumption in scenarios of active cooling strategies. In blue, Mechanical Ventilation; in red, Air Conditioning – aware; in orange, Air Conditioning – fixed. Each column is followed by a brighter one which represents the results of the retrofitted envelope.

Figure 9 shows the energy consumption per day of summer (kWh/day) of the active cooling strategies analysed. Mechanical Ventilation has a much lower consumption than any air conditioning scenario. The effect of retrofit on this strategy loses efficacy in the future (38% decrease in 2018, 18% in 2022 and 6% and 4% in 2030 and 2050 respectively). If air conditioning is used, the power consumption becomes higher than 13 kWh/day and therefore the cost for the household occupants. Nevertheless, an aware user can reduce averagely by 15% their energy consumption. Retrofit plays a more decisive role in future scenarios, as implementing it in 2022 causes a reduction of 7% and energy consumption for both the aware and fixed scenarios. In 2030, the savings are up to 13%. On the contrary, the beneficial effect is lower in 2050, probably due to the increased severity of the weather conditions.

Figure 10 – Scatter of the different strategies plotted twice (actual summers, AS, and future summers, FS) based on their energy consumption (horizontal axis) and time spent in CAT I (vertical axis). Both quantities are calculated over the simulated period June-September.

Figure 10 indeed correlates the energy consumption of different scenarios with the overall time spent in CAT I of Adaptive Comfort over the whole considered summer period. Each scenario is plotted twice: once it represents the average values obtained with data from 2018 and 2022 (actual summers, AS) and once with the average result obtained from 2030 and 2050 (future summers, FS). It is possible to identify three regions of the graph in which strategies fall. On the top-left, there are strategies which have low (or null) energy consumption but grant little comfort in the house (less than 50% of the time in CAT I). This area contains Natural Ventilation – fixed (both retrofit and not) and the future summer scenario of Natural Ventilation – aware. On the bottom left, there are strategies with low energy consumption and high comfort (i.e. more than 50% in CAT I), like Natural Ventilation – aware and Mechanical Ventilation. On the bottom right there are all the Air Conditioning scenarios, which have high energy consumption and high comfort. It can be noticed the big gap there is between ventilation measures and air conditioning ones, and how similar levels of comfort can be achieved in current summers but probably not in future ones. In general, points tend to create a hyperbole with two asymptotes.

Figure 11 – Zoom on High comfort – low consumption zone from Figure 10.

Figure 12 - Zoom on High comfort – high consumption zone from Figure 10.

Figure 11 and Figure 12 show respectively a zoom on High comfort – low consumption and High – comfort – high consumption zones. Lines connect points from the values obtained with data from 2018 - 2022 to the ones obtained with 2030 – 2050. In general, it can be noticed how in the future points are generally shifted up-right, which means lower comfort and higher consumption. The retrofit instead, helps to bring points down (meaning higher comfort) and to the left (lower consumption). Circles want to give an idea of where the points are placed in future summers respect to future ones. While in Figure 11, with ventilation, the region of actual and future summers are separated, in Figure 12 they tend to overlap, as points are much closer and there is not a big difference, especially for what regards time spent in CAT I (vertical axis).

4 CONCLUSIONS

The present paper makes an investigation on cooling strategies for extreme climatic events of intense heat caused by climate change. The strategies included passive strategies from vernacular knowledge like natural ventilation and solar shading, as such as active measures like mechanical ventilation with desk and ceiling fans, and air conditioning. A comparison is made to understand how relevant the behaviour of the user is to comfort and energy consumption. Additionally, each strategy is combined with a retrofit of the building as a mitigation action, to highlight the impact of the envelope on the inhabitants' lives. Simulations are performed with current meteorological data and future projections.

Ventilation strategies can grant a good level of comfort during current years (although not during heatwave periods), compared to the level provided by air conditioning. Nevertheless, they seem to be less and less effective as the years pass and climate change proceeds. The results suggest air conditioning will grant higher comfort in future years. Considering that 45% of the building stock of this category in Catalonia is not provided with any AC system (42), almost half of the population will be exposed to dangerous conditions during heat waves if this percentage does not change. On the other hand, massive use of air conditioning systems, especially during peaks of heat will have consequences on the electric grid, and anthropogenic heat besides the overall energy consumption.

The behaviour of the user is more helpful than just a retrofit. It increases the comfort band and reduces consumption at the same time. In the case of natural ventilation, adopting an aware behaviour instead of fixed can increase the time spent in CAT I and II during heatwaves between 4 and 32 times depending on the scenario. It also averagely saves 15% of the energy consumption for air conditioning, while implementing a retrofit around 7.5%.

Different indicators might lead to very different results, although the trend is the same. Adaptive comfort is less strict and, if CAT I and II are considered as “comfortable”, large portions of time fall in this category already for NATVENT-A or MECVENT. If HI or H are considered, and only normal and little to no discomfort are considered, respectively, as acceptable conditions, the situation is much worse. This might be due also because they take into account the relative humidity, which is averagely quite high in the coastal area of Barcelona.

Mechanical ventilation with fans does not have a relevant impact according to all the comfort indicators. HI and H are not able to quantify their impact. Nevertheless, when considering the thermal resilience of a building, it looks like it can help keep a constant comfort level even when external temperature escalates.

Further work has to be done in this field to reach even more accurate results. The climate projections used in the present study are done taking into account the foreseen CO₂ emission scenarios by IPCC (33) but do not consider the specific microclimate of urban areas, which suffers from the urban heat phenomenon. Additionally, it is realistic considering that in the future, more and more efficient buildings will be available (more Nearly Zero Energy Building), and they should be considered as well in the simulations. For what regards the comfort models selected, they will probably change in the future as the response of people will positively adapt after being exposed to increasingly higher levels of heat.

5 ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The research conducted is performed in the framework of the project “2020PANDE00116 - ComMit-20 Designing Resilient Communities to Mitigate Pandemic and Climate Change effects”, funded by the AGAUR (Agència de Gestió d’Ajust Universitaris i de Recerca).

6 REFERENCES

1. Berro DC. 11 agosto 2021, 48,8 °C in Sicilia. Nimbus Web [Internet]. 2021; Available from: <http://www.nimbus.it/eventi/2021/210811CaldoRecordSicilia.htm>
2. Arizona State University. World Meteorological Organization Global Weather & Climate Extremes Archive [Internet]. 2021 [cited 2022 Sep 7]. Available from: <https://wmo.asu.edu/content/world-meteorological-organization-global-weather-climate-extremes-archive>
3. Agencia Estatal de Meteorología. Agosto de 2021 termina con los récords de temperatura más alta jamás registrados hasta la fecha en 19 puntos de España [Internet]. 2021 [cited 2022 Sep 7]. Available from: https://www.aemet.es/es/noticias/2021/09/resumen_clima_agosto_2021

4. Agencia Estatal de Meteorología. Julio de 2022, el mes más cálido en España desde que hay registros [Internet]. 2022 [cited 2022 Sep 7]. Available from: https://www.aemet.es/es/noticias/2022/08/avance_julio_2022
5. Meteo.cat | Servei Meteorològic de Catalunya. L'estiu més càlid registrat a Catalunya [Internet]. 2022. Available from: <https://govern.cat/salaprensa/notes-premsa/436822/1-estiu-mes-calid-registrat-a-catalunya>
6. Santamouris M. Minimizing Energy Consumption, Energy Poverty and Global and Local Climate Change in the Built Environment: Innovating to Zero: Causalities and Impacts in a Zero Concept World. Elsevier; 2018.
7. Ajuntament de Barcelona. Pla Clima 2018-2030. Pla Clima. 2018;162.
8. Tham S, Thompson R, Landeg O, Murray KA, Waite T. Indoor temperature and health: a global systematic review. *Public Health* [Internet]. 2020;179:9–17. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.puhe.2019.09.005>
9. Lima F, Ferreira P, Leal V. Temperature and Health Outcomes. *Energies*. 2020;13(2881):1–24.
10. Ortiz J, Casquero-Modrego N, Salom J. Health and related economic effects of residential energy retrofitting in Spain. *Energy Policy* [Internet]. 2019;130(April):375–88. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2019.04.013>
11. Gasparrini A, Guo Y, Hashizume M. Mortalité attribuable au froid et à la chaleur : Analyse multi-pays. *Environnement, Risques et Sante*. 2015;14(6):464–5.
12. Royé D, Sera F, Tobías A, Lowe R, Gasparrini A, Pascal M, et al. Effects of Hot Nights on Mortality in Southern Europe. *Epidemiology*. 2021;(July):487–98.
13. Alberdi JC, Díaz J, Montero JC, Mirón I. Daily mortality in Madrid community 1968-1992: Relationship with meteorological variables. *Eur J Epidemiol*. 1998;(14):571–8.
14. Kairós - MOMO [Internet]. 2022 [cited 2022 Oct 5]. Available from: <https://momo.isciii.es/kairos/#section-documentación>
15. Kong D, Liu H, Wu Y, Li B, Wei S, Yuan M. Effects of indoor humidity on building occupants' thermal comfort and evidence in terms of climate adaptation. *Build Environ* [Internet]. 2019;155(March):298–307. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.buildenv.2019.02.039>
16. Baquero MT, Forcada N. Thermal comfort of older people during summer in the continental Mediterranean climate. *J Build Eng* [Internet]. 2022;54(May):104680. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jobte.2022.104680>
17. Klein RJT, Nicholls RJ, Thomalla F. Resilience to natural hazards: How useful is this concept? *Environ Hazards* [Internet]. 2003 Jan 1 [cited 2022 Oct 4];5(1):35–45. Available from: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/222394834_Resilience_to_natural_hazards_How_useful_is_this_concept

18. Resilient Cities Network. Urban resilience [Internet]. 2022 [cited 2022 Oct 4]. Available from: <https://resilientcitiesnetwork.org/urban-resilience/>
19. Rahmah W, Zaki M, Nawawi AH, Ahmad SS. Environmental Prospective of Passive Architecture Design Strategies in Terrace Houses. 2012;42(July 2010):300–10. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2012.04.194>
20. Kuczyński T, Staszczuk A, Gortych M, Stryjski R. Effect of thermal mass, night ventilation and window shading on summer thermal comfort of buildings in a temperate climate. *Build Environ*. 2021;204(July).
21. Schünemann C, Olfert A, Schiela D, Gruhler K, Ortlepp R. Mitigation and adaptation in multifamily housing: overheating and climate justice. *Build Cities*. 2020;1(1):36–55.
22. Linden P, Adams K, Daish N, Brunswick S, Banks D, Arens E, et al. Natural Ventilation for Energy Savings in California. 2016;
23. Agrawal PC. A review of passive systems for natural heating and cooling of buildings. 1989;(5):557–67.
24. Ortiz J, Fonseca A, Salom J, Garrido N, Fonseca P, Russo V. Comfort and economic criteria for selecting passive measures for the energy refurbishment of residential buildings in Catalonia. *Energy Build* [Internet]. 2016;110:195–210. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2015.10.022>
25. Veselý M, Zeiler W. Personalized conditioning and its impact on thermal comfort and energy performance – A review. *Renew Sustain Energy Rev* [Internet]. 2014;34:401–8. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2014.03.024>
26. Zhang H, Arens E, Zhai Y. A review of the corrective power of personal comfort systems in non-neutral ambient environments. *Build Environ* [Internet]. 2015;91:15–41. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.buildenv.2015.03.013>
27. André M, Kamimura A, Bavaresco M, Giaretta RF, Fossati M, Lamberts R. Achieving mid-rise NZEB offices in Brazilian urban centres: A control strategy with desk fans and extension of set point temperature. *Energy Build*. 2022;259.
28. Tejero A, Ortiz J, Salom J. Evaluation Of Occupancy Impact In A Residential Multifamily nZEB Through A High Resolution Stochastic Model Institut de Recerca en Energia de Catalunya (IREC), Sant Adrià de Besòs (Barcelona), Spain Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya , Barcelona , S. 4th Build Simul Optim Conf. 2018;(September):11–2.
29. SCL. Trnsys 18. Sol Energy Lab Univ Wisconsin-Madison [Internet]. 2018;3:7–36. Available from: <http://www.trnsys.com/>
30. Agència de l’Habitatge de Catalunya. INFORME DE LES TIPOLOGIES DEFINITIVES. Barcelona; 2014.
31. Meteo.cat [Servei Meteorològic de Catalunya. Dades de l’estació automàtica de Badalona - Museu [Internet]. 2022. Available from: <https://www.meteo.cat/observacions/xema/dades?codi=WU>

32. Meteonorm. Meteonorm Software Worldwide irradiation data [Internet]. 2022. Available from: <https://meteonorm.com/en/>
33. Kaito C, Ito A, Kimura S, Kimura Y, Saito Y, Nakada T. Climate Change 2014, Synthesis Report. Vol. 218. 2000.
34. Barcelona Regional. Pla Clima, Capítol II, Onades de Calor. Pla Clima. 2017;9–10.
35. Langlois N, Pathologist F, Herbst J. Journal of Forensic and Legal Medicine Using the Excess Heat Factor (EHF) to predict the risk of heat related deaths. J Forensic Leg Med [Internet]. 2013;20(5):408–11. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jflm.2012.12.005>
36. Nairn J, Fawcett R, Ray D. CAWCR Technical Report No. 071: Modelling and understanding high impact weather: extended abstracts of the third CAWCR Modelling Workshop, 30 november - 2 December 2009, Melbourne, Australia. [Internet]. Proceedings of the CAWCR modelling 2009. 83–86 p. Available from: <http://scholar.google.com/scholar?hl=en&btnG=Search&q=intitle:Defining+and+predicting+Excessive+Heat+events+,+a+National+system#0>
37. BS Standards. BS 56925:1991 Code of practice for ventilation principles and designing for natural ventilation. 1991.
38. McIntyre DA. Three Approaches to Thermal Comfort. ASHRAE Trans; (United States). 1978;84:101–9.
39. Rohles FM, Jones BW, Konz SA. Ceiling fans as extenders of the summer comfort envelope. ASHRAE Trans; (United States). 1983;89:1A:245–63.
40. Nicol FG. Characterising Occupant Behaviour in Buildings: Towards a Stochastic Model of Occupant Use of Windows, Lights, Blinds, Heaters and Fans. Proc 7th Int IBPSA Conf Rio Janeiro, 13-15 August 2001. 2001;1073–8.
41. He Y, Chen W, Wang Z, Zhang H. Review of fan-use rates in field studies and their effects on thermal comfort, energy conservation, and human productivity. Energy Build [Internet]. 2019;194:140–62. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2019.04.015>
42. Agència de l’Habitatge de Catalunya. RESULTATS DE L’ESTUDI DE CAMP. “CARACTERITZACIÓ DEL PARC Exist D’EDIFICIS D’HABITATGE CATALUNYA I Defin LES TIPOLOGIES MÉS Represent I EL PAQUET Mes PER A LA MILLORA D’EFICIÈNCIA ENERGÈTICA I LA SEVA AVALUACIÓ ECONÒMICA” D’EDIFICIS D’HABITATGE CATALUNYA I D. 2014;
43. Avanzini M, Ortiz J, Péan T, Cleries E, Borghero L, Salom J. Assessing natural ventilation strategies to improve thermal resilience to extreme temperatures of the residential buildings in Barcelona. In: 42nd AIVC Conference 10th TightVent Conference 8th venticool Conference Ventilation challenges in a changing world. Rotterdam; 2022. p. 143–52.
44. European Committee for Standardization. I.S. En 16798-1:2019. 2019;44(0). Available from: www.ili-info.com

45. UNI-EN ISO. ISO 7730:2005. 2006.
46. American Society of Heating Refrigerating And Air-Conditioning Engineering. Refrigerating, & American National Standards Institute. Therm Environ Cond Hum occupancy Vol 55. 2004;
47. American Society of Heating Refrigerating And Air-Conditioning Engineering. Thermal environmental conditions for human occupancy. ANSI/ASHRAE Standard 55 2017 p. 60.
48. Zhai Y, Arens E, Elsworth K, Zhang H. Selecting air speeds for cooling at sedentary and non-sedentary office activity levels. Build Environ [Internet]. 2017;122:247–57. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.buildenv.2017.06.027>
49. Rothfus LP. The Heat Index " Equation " (or , More Than You Ever Wanted to Know About Heat Index). 1979;1–2.
50. National Weather Service. NWS Experimental HeatRisk Overview Understanding the HeatRisk Product [Internet]. 2022 [cited 2022 Jul 13]. Available from: https://www.wrh.noaa.gov/wrh/heatrisk/pdf/HeatRisk_More_Info_Web.pdf
51. CSGNetwork.com. Canadian Humidex Calculator. 2011.
52. Environment Canada. Calculation of the 1971 to 2000 Climate Normals for Canada. 2013.
53. Hamdy M, Carlucci S, Hoes PJ, Hensen JLM. The impact of climate change on the overheating risk in dwellings—A Dutch case study. Build Environ [Internet]. 2017;122(August 2003):307–23. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.buildenv.2017.06.031>